

Lyrical Artistry and Musical Wizardry - Some Unique Compositions in Carnatic Music

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Abstract

Carnatic music has been enriched by a treasure of compositions from several eminent Composers who have used their imaginative and creative faculties to create unique musical forms. These genius musicians, popular and lesser known, have composed unique masterpieces with utmost fecundity. While some of these compositions are the result of musical wizardry, some are an innovative and intelligent blend of literary concepts and beauties with musical forms and lyrics. As a result, we have musical forms composed with the concepts of Svarakshara, Grahabheda, Anuloma-Viloma (Palindrome), Niroshtha, Raga Tala malika, Murchanakaraka, GarbhaKavitva, Bandha sahitya, Naamagopana, Manipravala, Yati, Prosody etc. Some of the genius composers who created such exceptional works are RamaswamiDikshitar, MuthuswamiDikshitar, Veena Kuppayyar, WalajapetaVenkataramanaBhagavatar, MahaVaidyanathaIyer, MuthaiahBhagavatar, MaddiralaVenkataraya Kavi, T.N.C.V. Narayanacharyulu, Adibhatla Narayana Dasu, Dr.MangalampalliBalamuralikrishna, N.Ch. Krishnamacharyulu, Prof. P. Sambamurthy etc. As there is every need to bring to light such intriguing concepts and the variety and uniqueness of such compositions in Carnatic Music, a humble attempt is being made to present them through this research paper.

Keywords

Rare Compositions, Unique Music Concept, Carnatic Music, Literary Concepts, South Indian Music, Vaggeyakaras

1. Introduction

Carnatic Classical Music, the traditional aesthetic art form of South India, is rich in melodious musical forms and complex rhythms, construed within the framework of a large number of ragas and talas. Several prolific Composers have made enormous contributions in enriching the vast repertoire of Carnatic Music. From this gamut, innovative and unique compositions of many an eminent Vaggeyakara have had a significant impact in the blossoming of literary and artistic treasure of Carnatic Music, which is a judicious mix of composition and improvisation.

There are several genius musicians, popular and lesser known, who have composed unique musical forms using their imaginative and creative faculties. While some of these compositions are the result of musical wizardry, some are an innovative, intelligent blend of literary concepts and beauties through music and lyric.

Though not exhaustive, this is a humble attempt to present a few compositions which demonstrate the rave musical and literary concepts and some exceptional compositions fused with the knowledge and spirituality of the prodigious composers.

2. Rave Concepts and Unique Compositions

Carnatic Music has a wide variety of Musical forms meant for learning and performance modes and each of these has a certain standard musical and lyrical structure. Compositions are an aesthetic presentation of raga-s woven with the intense feeling of devotion experienced by the composer. Innovative thinking and virtuosity of many composers resulted in the creation of a considerable number of extraordinary compositions infused with music and lyric.

Some of these concepts are - Svarakshara, Anuloma-Viloma (Palindrome), Grahabheda, Niroshtha, Raga Tala malika, Murchanakaraka, GarbhaKavitva, Bandha sahitya, Naamagopana, Manipravala, Yati, Prosody etc. A few representative examples are :

2.1 *Svarakshara*

‘Svarakshara, as the word itself implies, is a confluence of svara and akshara, where the svara syllable has the identical or like sounding syllable in the sahitya. These svaraksharas convey some meaning by themselves or with other non-svarakshara syllables’ (Sambamurthy, 2001) It is a technical and structural beauty which requires a literary skill of high order to compose. An aesthetic presentation distinctive to Carnatic music, it has been successfully employed by many composers for enhancing the musical and lyrical values of various musical forms like Gitam, Svarajati, Varnam, Kriti, Padam, Javali etc.

For example : 1. In the Charanam of Navaragamalikavarnam, composed by Kothavasal VenkataramaIyer - pada sarOja (pa da sa – is the svarakshara)

2. RamaswamiDikshitarcomposed a SvarasthanaVarnam in Todi raga set to Adi tala, in praise of his patron Manali VenkatakrishnaMudaliar

Pallavi : sarigAnidAnipAmarininI padasamAgamamAganIganinisA

Anupallavi : garimamadAripadArisadArigamapadanIdAnigAnIdAnipasagani

Charanam : marimariganisAganipanidagadanimanigAnigAnimmanigadA

marinIpathamamanigamarInigamaNalivenkaTakRishNEndranAthO

Here, the sahyam in Telugu uses only the seven letters sa, ri, ga, ma, pa, da, ni. The telugu words in the sahyam of this pada varNam are constructed skillfully using these seven letters. In addition to several popular composers who infused svarakshara concept in several melodic phrases, a lesser known eminent Vainika and Composer, Sri T.N.C.V. Narayanacharyulu, also composed several suchSvarakshara compositions.

2.2 Anuloma-Viloma (Palindrome)

Going by the lexicon, a ‘Palindrome’ is a word, sentence or a number that can be read the same way forward and backward(Dictionary, 2023). It is derived from the Greek word ‘Palindromos’, which means ‘running back again’. Usage of Palindromes in writings primarily displays the literary intellect of the scholarly writers and their technical brilliance in the skill of writing with the constraint of palindromic form, which is both challenging and entertaining.

Though the literature in languages like Sanskrit, Telugu and Tamil are abound in palindrome words, in the context of music, we come across a very few composers who have attempted this literary concept, blending it with melodic structures in musical forms. A few Composers who composed palindromic compositions are - RamaswamiDikshitar (Daru in Sanskrit), ThirugnanaSambandhar (Thevaram in Tamil), King Shahaji (Savyaapasavyasama pada lilaDaru in Revagupti raga, Adi Tala), WalajapetaVenkataramanaBhagavatar and Vina Kuppayyar (Varnam in Raga Bhairavi, set to Adi Talam – (Telugu)).

Let’s see a few illustrations–

1. The anulomaprtilomaDaru (Sanskrit) of RamaswamiDikshitar in the raga Gangatarangini, set to Trisra Eka talam is -

Pallavi : sArasanayanasarasA - sAratararatarasA

Anupallavi : mAratAtataramA – amanita madhyamatanimA
mAnitamadhyamatanimAtArapabhaparatatApitavayavatApitA

Charanam : bhArambhAtamitabhArambhAbhAvarAgatAlatAgarAvabhA
bhAratEtava ta terabhAsAnapatitapatitamanasA
hAravidhirodhivirahAhAvananatAnanavahA
sAratumetu me sarasAsakhivenkaTakRishNasarasa

2. Now, let's see the lyric of the Varnam (Telugu) :

Pallavi : sarasakurAkusarasa - varamanasunamarava

Anupallavi : para veladulaverapa - nAravamanumavaranA

Caraṇam : rAjIvanayanavajIrA

It is interesting to note that this composition is in a Palindrome form in both svara and sahitya. For example : **Pallavi** begins as -

Ś , Ś , N , D , , , P , M P tD N |
sa . ra . sa ku rā |
N D P M P , tD , | , , N , Ś , Ś , ||
. ku | sa . ra . sa . ||

2.3 *Grahabheda / Murchanakaraka*

Grahabhedam is the process of shifting the tonic note, Adhara shruti, to another note in the same raga, thereby arriving at a different raga (Gayatri, 2015). The pure positions of the notes are maintained but they assume different colours. It is like a new raga within the old raga. Musicians have used grahabhedam as the focal point in their compositions. Examples are Dr.M. Balamuralikrishna's Tillana in Kalyani, Tanjore S. Kalyanaraman's composition in Sindhubhairavi and Lalgudi G. Jayaraman's Svarajati composition in Sindhubhairavi.

Prof.Sambhamurthy's creativity has brought out two unusual compositions- the sutra gita-

s illustrating grahabheda. (modal shift). One is 'Shankara todikalhari nata' in the ragam Shankarabharanam and another one is 'Mohanamadhyahindolasuddhodayaravichandrika' in the ragam Mohana. The lyrics enable a student to remember the raga-s that arise when grahabheda is performed in each svara of the scale. Another example is that he has also composed a 'MurchanakaraMela Ragamalika', which gives the scales that arise out of each mela raga by modal shift of tonic and the svara-s that come out of these scales.

2.4 *Niroshtha*

Niroshta literally means without using the lips. If the lips do not meet / touch, then the notes Ma and Pa cannot be uttered. This kind of scale does not use either notes and hence the name. It is a very unique concept and a pleasing ragam. In the 72 melakarta scheme, there is a mathematical possibility for several raga-s with Niroshtha concept, so each of these arising from the 72 mela-s has a different name with different aesthetics, due to the inherent quality of notes. MuthiahBhagavatar is credited with creating this concept and scale of Putrika as a janya of 29th mela Dhirasankarabharanam. His melodious composition 'Raja RajaRadhite' set to Rupaka tala does not use the syllables Ma and Pa, not just in the svara part but also in the sahitya. Madurai T. N. Seshagopalan, a disciple of Ramanathapuram C. S. Sankarasivam, who in turn is a disciple of MuthiahBhagavatar has composed a Tillana in Niroshtha - 'Tanana dhirana' in Adi Tala. Tanjavur. S. Kalyanaraman has composed a Varnam 'Kanin Maniye' in this raga. Other compositions with such a concept include 'Giri-putrikagaura-varni' by Bangalore S Mukund in Rupakatalam and 'Jayatijayatijayashankara' by Ashok R Madhav in Rupaka tala.

2.5 *Naamagopana*

This is yet another interesting and intriguing feature in Carnatic music compositions and lyrical aspects. 'Nama Gopana' indicates that there is a hidden message in the composition which can be decoded by joining the first letters in all the sections of the composition. 'Samba paraakaSarvaparaaka', is a 'Nama GopanaKirthana' penned by a lesser known Telugu vaggeyakara, Sri MaddiralaVenkatarayakavi in his GeyaPrabandha 'Ekanta Seva Vilasamu'

Pallavi : sAmbaparAkAsharvaparAkA- shankara hara shiva shambhOparAkA ||

Charanams : bAdarAyaNAdibahumaunisannuta pada Padma shrIvIrabhadraparAkA||

huMkAramunadakShunipoMkamaNachinapaMkajAkShavIrabhadra ||

IEtajiMkadAlchilIlatOnaTiyiMchupAtaka hara vIrabhadra ||

dRikkarNabhUShaNadIpasaMrakShaNavaAkkAMtAnutavIrabhadra ||

lakShmIramaNabANarAjitashrIrAjyalakshmIpavIralalAmaparAkA ||

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.....

sEviMtumimujAladIviMtumadilOnabhAviMtushrIvIrabhadra ||

yamaniyamAdya.ShtAMgayOgapadmabhramararUpavIrabhadra ||

varaduDavaimammugaruNiMpusirulicchiparamAtmashrIvIrabhadra ||

lakShalaDugalEdurakShiMpumaMTinipakShamuMchivIrabhadra ||

yuddhabhImajaguddhArayAjnakubaddhuDashrIvIrabhadra ||

nUruyugaMbulupEruvahiMpumIpauruShamunavIrabhadra ||

vaTTisamAdhAnameTTusammatiMtupaTTisashrIvIrabhadra ||

karuNiMpushrIpIThApurakukkuTEshvaravararUpashrIvIrabhadra ||

lAlitashrImaddirAlavEMkatarAyaDIIAguvEDavIrEshaparAkA ||

- We can observe from the sahitya given above that the highlighted first letters of each of these Charanams, when put together, give the message ‘bAhulEMdrulasItArAmayyagArU ! mA tammulakuvivAhamulusEyavalayu’ and the last four lines sum up the composer’s intent in pleading Lord Kukkutesvara (the form of Virabhadra) regarding the decoded message. The meaning of this hidden message is that the composer is seeking a monetary blessing for performing the marriage of his brothers.

2.6 Varna Krama

In the ‘Varna Krama Kirthana’, each of the Charanams begins with an alphabet in the Telugu Script (all the Vowels and Consonants), in a series. ‘Samba SadasivaSankara hara’, is a ‘Varna Krama Kirthana’ penned by a lesser known Telugu vaggeyakara, Sri MaddiralaVenkatarayakavi in his GeyaPrabandha ‘Ekanta Seva Vilasamu’

Pallavi : sAmbasadAshivashaMkara hara jagadaMbaramaNapAhiliMgaprabhO ||

Charanams : adrIMdrakanyAsuhRdrAjitAkArachidrUpadhaurEyaliMgaprabhO ||

AdyaMtashUnyAtmavidyAnumEyAbhivAdyOruchAritraliMga ||

indrAdivaMdyArkachaMdrAgninEtrAchalEMdranutAdhIshaliMga ||

IShaNatrayadu:khadUShaNabhOgIMdrabhUShaNamAMpAhiliMga ||

uddhULitAnaMgashuddhAMgabhasmaprasiddhAmitOIlAsaliMga ||

UrupradEshasthirArUDhagaurIkuchArOpitOraskataliMga ||

.....

kaMjAtakiMjalkapUriprabhAjUTashiMjAnamaMjIraliMga ||

.....

.....

kShaMtavyOmEniraMtaramaparAdhashshAMtashshivAkAMtaliMga ||

akSharakaruNAkaTAKShavEMkaTarAyatakShaNapIThApurasthapra ||

gaMgAdharAsarvamaMgaLAhRdayAbjabhRMgashrIkukkuTaliMgaprabhO ||

We can observe from the sahitya given above that the highlighted first letters of all the Charanams, represent each and every alphabet of the Telugu aksharamala, beautifully woven into the sahitya of the composition.

2.7 Yoga

‘PurnaChidanandaYogire’is yet another Kirtana composed by the lesser known Telugu vaggeyakara, Sri MaddiralaVenkatarayakavi in his GeyaPrabandha ‘Ekanta Seva Vilasamu’which reveals the composer’s proficiency in Yoga, as the composition deals with Seven Chakras of the etheric body (Muladhara, Svadhishtana, Manipura, Anahata, Vishuddha, Ajna and Sahasrara) describing the features such as number of petals, the matruka letters, number of colours etc., of each chakra.

Pallavi : pUrNachidAnaMdayOgIrEpIThapurakukkuTEshvarayOgIrE ||

Charanams: AdhAra kamala vasAMta *varNashrayahastimukhAbhikhyayOgIrE ||

bAlAMtaShaDvarNabhAsurAdhiShThAna brahma svarUpakayOgIrE ||

DAdiphakarAMtadashadaLamaNipUraKodavivArirUpayOgIrE ||

.....

unmanassaukhyamahOIlAsakAraNatanmayarUpakayOgIrE ||

varaNAIsaMgamavaragurupadasaktasthirachittasatpradayOgIrE ||

karuNAkaTAKShavIkShaNalabdhayOkavEmkaTarAyapOShaNayOgIrE ||

2.8 Raga Malika / Raga Tala malika

The word Ragamalika means a garland of ragas and Talamalika is a garland of talas and these are compositions where different segments of the same song are set to different ragas and talas. There are several Ragamalika compositions incorporated in the musical forms of Abhyasa and Sabha ganam. Gitam-s, Ghana raga Pancakavarnam where the Pallavi is in Nata, the Anupallavi in Gaula, the Mukhtayi in Arabhi, the first Charanam in Varali and all five ragas appear in the last Charanam. Veena Venkatesvara Raja's varnam has the first three as in Vinjamuri's but the Charanams have ragas from the second set of Ghana ragas – Bauli, Kedaram, Narayanagaula. The Behagvarnam of Veena Seshanna has the last ettugada in 14 ragas, Navaragamalika of Kothavasal Venkatarama Iyer has Nine ragas in the varnam one each for each section in the purvanga and uttaranga, except for the mukhtayisvarnam which has two ragas in it.

Prof. Sambhamurthy has created a varnam called 'Dina-ragamalika' containing 8 ragams. To pose a challenge in singing a varnam, N.C. Parthasarathi's 'Nakshatra malika' varnam comprises 27 ragams, in which each avartam has two ragams.

Sri Ajjada Adibhatla Narayana Dasu has composed a Ragamalika composition titled 'Dasavidha raga navatikusumamanjari' with 90 ragas, where the first part is sung in the first speed and the second half is sung in the second speed with all these 90 ragas sung in the reverse order. This composition can be sung to all the five jati-s of eka talam.

Ramaswamy Dikshitar (father of Muthuswami Dikshitar) has been credited to have composed several ragamalikas. He has also composed the 'Ashtottarasata raga tala malika', the longest known with 108 ragas and 108 talas.

Muthuswami Dikshitar's 'Chaturdasharagamalika' with 14 ragams is also very well known.

In this class of ragamalika compositions, mention should also be made of Maha Vaidyanatha Iyer's '72 melakarta composition' featuring all the 72 mela ragas. This is in praise of Lord Pranatharthihara, the presiding deity at Tiruvaiyaru Temple. Historically, the first person to compose a 72 melakartha ragamalika was one Lavani Venkata Rao. This was composed as a eulogy for the then Maharaja of Tanjavur.

A few vaggeyakaras have even attempted composing raga-tala-malika, in which ragam and talam vary for each avartam. Subbarama Dikshitar, in his 'Raga-Tala-Malika' has used all the Suladi Sapta Tala-s. It is given that Pratapa Simha Maharaja of Tanjavur has composed a raga-tala-malika in Marathi with intricate swara patterns.

The last piece in any concert is mangalam, which is usually simple in structure set in one ragam. The uncommon mangalam by Krishnaswamy Ayya contains 11 raga-s.

2.10 *GarbhaKavitva*

This is a very unique literary concept used in Telugu and Sanskrit literature. In this, the same lyrics of a Kriti could be set to more than one Tala structure by reducing a few sahityaaksharas and still make meaningful sahitya, completely conforming to the prosodical rules. Sri N. Ch.Krishnamacharyulu, an eminent Scholar, Musician, Teacher and Harikatha exponent, has composed 3 such compositions in Sanskrit, which employ more than one talam for the same kriti. Sri N.Ch.Krishnamacharyulu was a pioneer in developing this kind of compositions. They are:

1. Sri Rama Ramana - Vachaspati - RupakaGarbha Adi Talam
2. PahimamPahi - Harikambhoji - JhampeGarbha Adi Talam
3. Neerajaksha - ShuddhaDhanyasi - JhampeTriputaGarbha Adi Talam

2.11 *Bandha sahitya*

Bandha Kavitvam is a type of figured and ornate poetry which is of a very complicated pattern. Only a few have attempted it and this rare concept has been taken up by Sri T.N.C.V. Narayanacharyulu, an eminent Vainika, to be composed as Svara compositions on some of the well known bandhas. Following the Patterns of bandha-s, svara passages have been composed, which include – Ashtadala Padma bandha, malika bandha, guchha bandha, chakra bandha, kundalinaaga bandha etc.,

2.12 *Yati*

When it comes to svara patterns, varnam composers would appear to have used their imagination to the fullest. There are varnams with Vadi-Samvadi usage (ga ga - nini usages in MuthiahBhagavatar'sKhamas raga Daru Varnam – 'mAtE'). The same note in different sthayis is used for instance by KothavasaVenkataramaIyer in his Sama raga varnam. The same note is repeated to good effect by SubbaramaDikshitar in his Nata ragavarnam. The Kambhoji raga padavarnam of Ramasvami Sivan displays usage of mridanga, gopuccha and pippilika (sama) yatis.

2.13 *Prosody*

It is also learnt that there are varnams based on metre/chandas as well andavarnam in raga Navaroju has several metres such as mattehba, dvipada, utpala and champakamala.

2.14 *Manipravala*

'Manipravalam' refers to the harmonious blend of more than one language in a single Composition. It is a hybrid language used as a literary style by the medieval poets and

music composers in South India. Generally, compositions are written in only one language. But several composers of Carnatic Music have used more than one language to create manipravala compositions. Muthuswami Dikshitar had composed three manipravala compositions, where he has used 3 different languages like Sanskrit, Telugu and Tamil. They are: Sri Abhayambanin in the raga Sri, Venkatachalapate and Sri Maharajni, both in the raga Karnataka Kapi.

The Travancore Maharaja Swati Tirunal had composed 15 Manipravala kritis using Malayalam and Sanskrit. An illustrious musician and disciple of Thyagaraja, Sri Walajapeta Venkataramana Bhagavata also composed manipravala compositions using Telugu and Saurashtra. Other composers like Prof. Sambhamurthy, Bangalore S. Mukund etc., have also attempted similar compositions.

It is also very interesting to note that Sri Karur Shivaramaiah has composed a javali in English and Telugu in the raga Kharaharapriya set to Adi Talam. The lyric is as follows -

Pallavi : O my lovely lalan A E lan Epomma NTi

Anupallavi : Em Oyan Iyu NTi k Amin Innu

Charanam 1 : kaugalimpuv ELak Antan Iv ADinadikapa Tam ATalan ikanugo NTini

Charanam 2 : iTUva NTi step -is it fit to take, sit a while here, let me convince you

Charanam 3 : evarivaddanudon't be angry shivar Amunipadamub ADu

2.15 Mnemonics

Musical Mnemonics is a technique used as an aid to remember musical facts, laws and phenomena relating to the science of music. Mnemonics are applied to nomenclatures of Sruti-s, Svara-s, Mela-s, Raga-s and Tala-s. When the art of printing was not available, raga lakshana-s were learnt with the aid of Lakshana Gita-s. Further, the svara variations were assigned syllables using the vowel changes and the note frequencies would be easily revealed. For example – 3 variations of Rishabham (Suddha, Chatussruti and Shatsruti) would be referred as Ra, Ri, Ru, respectively. Similarly it is Ga, Gi, Gu, Ma, Mi, Dha, Dhi, Dhu and Na, Ni, Nu for other svaras which have variations in notes. This concept was resorted to in the Raganga Raga Lakshana Gita-s composed by Venkatamakhi.

For example – in the Raganga Raga Lakshana Gita in Raga Sankarabharana, the first six avarta-s have the initial syllables as – ri, gu, ma, pa, dhi, nu, indicating the svara variations occurring in this raga - ripubalakhanda nure – guru gunakarure – mayaparataru re – paripalita bhuvanure – dhijanarakshana nure – nutacharitarure

2.16 Rare Tala-s

Tillanas in general are set in common tala-s like Adi, MisraChapu and Rupakam. Poochi Srinivasa Iyengar has composed two tillanas in uncommon talams. The first tillana is set to 108 aksharatalam called 'Lakshmisam' and the second tillana with 72 aksharatalam called 'Ragavardhani'. MahaVaidhyanathaIyer's stillana is set in Simhanandanatalam with 128 beats. A newer addition to the uncommon tillana is one with 35 aksharatalam, created by Chengalput Ranganathan.

3. Conclusion

It is indeed overwhelming to know and learn about such a great treasure in the performing art of Carnatic Music and its literature. There are many more such remarkable but lesser known and performed repertoire. By documenting these rare and exquisite musical forms, we will be handing over a rich musical legacy to posterity and also serve as an inspiration for bringing out many more such intriguing concepts.

REFERENCES

1. Balasubrahmanyam Vyzarsu and Pavani Vyzarsu, 'Ajnatha Vaggeyakarulu', Life and Music of lesser known Telugu Composers, Bhairavi Sangeeta Academy, Hyderabad, 2018
2. Krishnamacharyulu, N.Ch., 'Krishnamacharya Sangita Krutulu', Krishnamacharya Kalapeetham, Vijayawada, 2010
3. Lalitha Ramakrishna, 'The Varnam', Harman Publishing House, New Delhi, 1991.
4. Narayanacharyulu, T.N.C.V., sariga mA pAdasani Pancharatnamulu, Author's Publication, Guntur, 1951, pp 1-12
5. Narayanaswami P.P., Monumental Compositions of Ramaswami Dikshitar, <http://carnatica.net/special/rdikshitar.htm>
6. Published Notation, 'A Rare Tana Varna', The Journal of the Music Academy, Vol. XL, Chennai, 1969
7. Sambamoorthy, P. Prof., History of Indian Music, The Indian Music Publishing House, Chennai, 1998
8. Sambamoorthy, P. Prof., South Indian Music Book III, The Indian Music Publishing House, Chennai, 2001
9. Venkata Kavi, Maddirala, 'Ekanta Seva Vilasamu', published at Pithapuram, 1933

